

A Study on the Immobilization of Toxic Metal Ions by using Prepared Kaolinite and Fly Ash-based Geopolymers

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Abstract

Geopolymers are the synthetic analogues of natural zeolitic materials which are aluminosilicate materials. They can be used in the immobilization of heavy metal contaminants as well as in the structural products. Thus, the aim of this research work is to study the use of kaolinite and fly ash-based geopolymer to immobilize heavy and toxic metals in application of the removal of toxic metals from contaminated wastewater and the extraction of heavy metals from their leached solutions. The characterization of kaolinite samples from Taungnauk and Kyauktaga and fly ash samples from industries located at Tigyit and Pyin Oo Lwin were carried out by using EDXRF, SEM, XRD, FTIR and TG-DTA instrumental techniques. Moreover, the chemical compositions of the samples were also analyzed by using standard conventional methods. The geopolymer materials were prepared by using different ratios of kaolinite and fly ash with different concentrations of sodium hydroxide at room temperature. These geopolymer samples were analyzed and characterized by conventional methods and modern instrumental techniques such as EDXRF, SEM, XRD, FTIR and TG-DTA. Moreover, some mechanical properties of the prepared geopolymers, such as compressive strength and tensile strength were also carried out. Since this research work concerns with the use of geopolymers for immobilization of heavy and toxic metals, the removal of toxic metal ions in wastewater samples from different industries by using prepared geopolymer samples (H1-H4). Among the four geopolymer samples, geopolymer sample (H1) was found to be the maximum leaching property (i.e., the immobilization efficiency exceeds 92.9% when Pb^{2+} ions contained in metal loaded geopolymer (H1). Moreover, the removal percents of Pb^{2+} , Cd^{2+} and As^{3+} ions from wastewater samples were found to be in the range of 67.5%, 59.5% and 52.5% for Textile Mill (Wundwin), whereas the removal percents of Pb^{2+} and As^{3+} ions were 65.7% and 49.4% for Battery Industry (Shwe Pyi Thar) by using prepared geopolymer (H1). Thus the process of removal of the toxic metal ions from wastewater sample by kaolinite and fly ash-based geopolymers can be used as an effective aluminosilicate polymeric material in the treatment of industrial influents.

Key words: kaolinite, fly ash, geopolymers, wastewater, heavy and toxic metals, immobilization

Introduction

Geopolymer is a novel binding material produced from the reaction of kaolinite and fly ash with an alkaline solution. Geopolymers are inorganic polymeric binding materials, firstly developed by Joseph Davidovits in 1970s (Ravindra, 2009). Unlike conventional organic polymers, glass, ceramic, or cement, geopolymers are non-combustible, heat resistant, formed at low temperatures, and fire and acid resistant (Wang, 2003).

Geopolymers are a novel class of materials that are formed by the polymerization of silicon, oxygen, and aluminium species to form an amorphous three-dimensional framework structure. These materials are sometimes referred to as alkaline cements or geocements and the overall technology, which encompasses the polymerization of inorganic metal species, as inorganic polymer technology (Van Jaarsveld, 2004).

In order to produce geopolymer, low- calcium fly ash needs to be activated by an alkaline solution to produce polymeric Si-O-Al bonds. It is a class of three- dimensionally networked aluminosilicate materials, similar to natural zeolite minerals in chemical composition, but they reveal an amorphous microstructure (Djwantoro, 2008). Three common types of geopolymer are the polysialate Al-O-Si chain, polysialate siloxo Al-O-Si-Si chain

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and polysialate disiloxo Al–O–Si–Si–Si chain. Geopolymer has the potential to reduce greenhouse emissions from the cement industry by 80% (Xu, 2000).

During the last few decades, fly ash, slag, kaolinite, mine tailings, etc. are used as raw materials to synthesize geopolymers, of which kaolinite is most common for its relatively purer components (Zhang, 2007). Fly ash, which is rich in silica and alumina, has full potential to use as one of the source material for geopolymer binder. It is the main solid waste generated from the coal combustion in the power stations (Ravindra, 2009).

Each year, millions of tones of heavy metal contaminants such as mine tailings and electroplating sludge are generated across the worlds. These wastes are accumulated to such an extent that 'giga-scale disposal' is becoming a common phenomenon. In general, Pb, Cd and As are three prominent heavy metals in the wastes as compared to other types of heavy metals. Thus, studies on the immobilization of Pb, Cd and As are very important for testing a new type of heavy metal solidification materials (Yunsheng, 2006).

Geopolymer has the potential to replace ordinary portland cement concrete and produce fly ash- based geopolymer with excellent physical and mechanical properties. Geopolymer binders might be a suitable alternative in the development of acid resistant (Suresh, 2009). The geopolymer binders may be treated as future environmental friendly alternative to Portland cement in certain industrial applications. The other primary use of geopolymer technology in waste management is as a matrix for the immobilization of cationic radioactive or toxic contaminants (Van Deventer, 2007).

In this research work, a systematic analytical assay and characterization of local kaolinite and coal fly ash from different cement Industries were carried out. The composition, microstructure and influence on mechanical properties of prepared geopolymers were investigated. The compressive strength, tensile strength and setting time of kaolinite and fly ash-based prepared geopolymers were also determined. Moreover, the mineralogical and microstructural characteristics of geopolymeric materials were studied by means of SEM, EDXRF, XRD, FT IR and TG-DTA for explaining the changes in compressive strength of geopolymer samples. In order to better understand the immobilization behaviors of the geopolymer incorporated with fly ash, the prepared geopolymers can be utilized in the removal of heavy and toxic metal ions such as lead, cadmium and arsenic. Leaching tests were provided more substantial information regarding the immobilizing efficiency.

Materials and Methods

All the chemicals used were obtained from reagent grade (BDH). It comprised of sodium hydroxide, sodium silicate, $\text{Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2$, $\text{Cd}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ and As_2O_3 . The apparatus used consist of Balance (Sartorius AG Gottingen BL 2105, L. Switzerland, 210 g \pm 0.1 mg), Oven (Ambient 250 \pm 2°C, Griffin, England), Furnace (100–1100°C) (Model No. 9511028, Hohl-1995, Nabersheim, Germany), pH Meter (Jenway 4330, Labquip, England), X-ray Diffractometer (XRD-Rigaku-D-Max-2200, Japan), Energy Dispersive-X-ray Fluorescence Spectrometer (EDX-700, Shimadzu, Japan), SEM (Jeol-JSM-5610 LV model, Japan), FT-IR (Perkin Elmer 1600 Fourier Transform Infrared Spectrometer, Japan), TG-DTA (Hi-TGA 2950 Thermo gravimetric Analyzer), Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometer (Perkin Elmer Analyst 800) and Electric Shaker (0- 200 °C) (SBs- 30 Bibby, Stuart Scientific Shaker Bath, UK). And then the setting time, compressive strength and tensile strength were also assessed using standard moulds. Leaching of each particle size fraction of metal loaded geopolymers were conducted using a modified Toxicity Characteristic Leaching Procedure (TCLP) utilizing acetic acid buffered at pH = 4.5 by analytical grade sodium acetate.

Sample Collection

Kaolinite

Both kaolinite clay raw materials were procured from (1) Chauk's Ceramic Bulb Industry and (2) Development of Cement and Ceramic Technology, Danyingone. Representative kaolinite samples were produced from (1) Kyauktaga area and (2) Taungnauk area, near Popa Mountain, Kyaukpadaung Township, Mandalay Region. These samples were used in the present work. The beneficiated samples were bagged in cotton container. Sampling was carried out by *cone and quartering method*. The photographs of kaolinite samples (Kyauktaga and Taungnauk) are shown in Figures 1(a) and 1(b).

Fly Ash

Two fly ash samples were chosen for this investigation on the basis of two different coal sources. Representative coal fly ash samples were procured from Kyarkhaung Cement Industry, which is located at Pyin Oo Lwin, Mandalay Region. The coal was originated from Sin Taung Mine at Lashio Township, Northern Shan State. The photograph of Pyin Oo Lwin fly ash sample is shown in Figure 2 (a).

The other fly ash samples were received from Tigyit Cement Industry, which is located at Tigyit, Pinlaung Township in Southern Shan State. The coal was originated from Tigyit Mine at Pinlaung Township, Southern Shan State. The photograph of Tigyit fly ash sample is also shown in Figure 2 (b).

Figure 1. Photograph of kaolinite samples

Figure 2. Photograph of fly ash samples

Preparation of Kaolinite and Fly Ash-based Geopolymers

Different ratios of kaolinite and fly ash were mixed with the different concentrations of sodium hydroxide solutions and the same concentrations of sodium silicate solution on a non-absorbent base for various geopolymers. Immediately after mixing, the motor was placed in the hopper of the tube mould in one portion. This mould was vibrated with motor two minutes at full speed. Following vibration, the specimen was kept in moist closet. The specimen was removed from the mould after 24 h, and then prepared geopolymer specimens were stored in air-dry places at room temperature (Website 1).

Components of Sample Number for Prepared Geopolymers

Source materials	Kaolinite + Fly Ash	Prepared geopolymer samples
(1) Taungnauk	+ Tigyit	: A1 – I 1
(2) Taungnauk	+ Pyin Oo Lwin	: A2 – I 2
(3) Kyauktaga	+ Tigyit	: A3 – I 3
(4) Kyauktaga	+ Pyin Oo Lwin	: A4 – I 4

Mixing Amount of Source Materials for the Preparation of Geopolymers

Geopolymer	Mass ratio		Volume ratio		Concn. of NaOH (M)
	Kaolinite	Fly Ash	Na ₂ SiO ₃	NaOH	
A1 - A4	1	1	1	1	1
B1 - B4	1	1	2	3	1
C1 - C4	1	1	3	2	1
D1 - D4	1	1	1	1	8
E1 - E4	1(*0.4)	1	1	1.2	5
F1 - F4	3	4	2	3	3
G1 - G4	3	2	2	3	3
H1 - H4	4	3	2	3	3
I1 - I4	2	3	2	3	3

(* = Sand); [Na₂SiO₃] = 1M

Mechanical Properties of Prepared Geopolymers

The compressive and tensile strength of prepared kaolinite and fly ash-based geopolymers were determined at the age of 28 days. Moreover, the tensile strength test was repeated after 56 days. Some prepared geopolymers for measuring compressive and tensile strength are shown in Figure 3. Compressive testing machines are also shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Compressive strength and tensile strength measurement

Preparation of Pb, Cd and As Loaded Kaolinite and Fly Ash-based Geopolymers

Heavy metal cations (Pb²⁺, Cd²⁺ and As³⁺) were added to the reaction mixture during mixing as solutions of their nitrate salts [(Pb(NO₃)₂ and Cd(NO₃)₂] in water except in the case of arsenic where an oxide (As₂O₃) was used. Chemical grade sodium silicate and sodium hydroxide solutions with volume ratio of 2:3 were used as alkaline activator. It could well be noted that the amounts of sodium silicate and sodium hydroxide used in producing geopolymer samples H1-H4 was chosen as metal loaded geopolymers. The photographs for Pb, Cd and As loaded prepared geopolymer samples are shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4. Photographs of metal loaded prepared geopolymer samples (H1-H4)

Leaching Test for Immobilization of Toxic Metal Ions

In the case of metal loaded geopolymer samples (H1-H4) only the stirring technique was used with sampling being performed periodically until a 24 h period. Leaching of each particle size fraction was conducted using a modified Toxicity Characteristic Leaching Procedure (TCLP) utilizing acetic acid buffered at pH = 4.5 by analytical grade sodium acetate. A solid: liquid ratio of 1:25 was used for the leaching methods and the temperature was maintained at 30°C by a water bath. All samples were stirred at the mixing speed of 200 rpm by using the orbital shaker. The flasks were shaken with electric shaker for 2 h, 8 h and 24 h at room temperature. After shaking, the solutions were allowed to settle out. These solutions were filtered and the residual contents of Pb²⁺, Cd²⁺ and As³⁺ in the filtrate was determined by atomic absorption spectrophotometry (AAS) (Van Jaarsveld, 1997). The photograph of orbital shaker is shown in Figure 5.

Removal of Toxic Metal Ions (Pb²⁺, Cd²⁺ and As³⁺) from Industrial Wastewater

Wastewater samples were collected from (i) Textile Mills in Wundwin Industrial Zone, Mandalay Region, (ii) TOYO Battery in Shwe Pyi Thar Industrial Zone, Yangon Region, (iii) Metal Smelting Factory, Ayetharyar Industrial Zone (Taunggyi), Southern Shan State and (iv) Aluminium Ware Factory, Oakkyin, Yangon Region. The photograph for source of wastewater sample from Textile Mills in Wundwin Industrial Zone is shown in Figure 6.

Figure 5. Photograph of orbital shaker

Figure 6. Photograph of wastewater sample (Textile Mills in Wundwin Industrial Zone)

Results and Discussion

Analytical Assay of Kaolinite and Fly Ash Samples

Chemical constituents (loss on ignition, SiO₂, Al₂O₃, Fe₂O₃, CaO and MgO and SO₃) of both kaolinite and fly ash samples were determined according to the standard method of analysis of ceramic materials (Hikichi, 1998). The chemical analytical assay data of these samples are represented in Table 1. From the wet analysis, percent content of SiO₂ in Taungnauk kaolinite sample was found to be contained the highest silica (68.48 %). By this method, percent contents of Al₂O₃ were observed 36.94% in Kyauktaga kaolinite sample, whereas 19.48% in Taungnauk kaolinite sample. Tigyit fly ash sample was found to be contained the highest SiO₂ content (36.54%) and Al₂O₃ content (14.36%). Pyin Oo Lwin fly ash sample was observed lower SiO₂ content (15.44%) and Al₂O₃ content (5.64%).

Table1. Analytical Assay of Kaolinite and Fly Ash Samples from two Different Localities

Oxide (%)	Kaolinite Sample		Fly Ash Sample	
	Taungnauk	Kyauktaga	Tigyit	Pyin Oo Lwin
SiO₂	68.48	48.18	36.54	15.44
Al₂O₃	19.48	36.94	14.36	5.64
Fe₂O₃	1.68	0.96	5.76	3.36
CaO	0.04	0.07	31.59	40.84
MgO	2.58	0.81	2.03	2.16
SO₃	-	-	5.94	7.30
LOI*	5.51	12.72	2.50	15.35
Total	97.77	99.68	98.72	90.09

LOI* = Loss on Ignition

Characterization of Kaolinite and Fly Ash Samples

Kaolinite clay minerals and coal fly ash samples were semi-quantitatively analyzed by EDXRF spectrometer. According to EDXRF semi-quantitative analysis, it can be observed that silica (SiO₂) contents were found to be the highest in both kaolinite samples. These samples were also qualitatively characterized by X-ray diffractometer. From the XRD diffractograms, SiO₂ and Al₂O₃ were observed in both clay minerals and fly ash samples (Figures 7 (a) and 7 (b)). SEM was also analyzed to describe the morphology of source materials. The SEM photomicrographs of kaolinite and fly ash samples presented in (Figures 8 and 9) are observed as crystalline nature and amorphous nature respectively.

The FTIR spectra of Taungnauk kaolinite and Tigyit fly ash samples are shown in Figures 10 (a) and 10 (b). The band assignments of both kaolinite and fly ash samples are tabulated in Table 2. According to FTIR data, the bands at 1095cm⁻¹(Si-O symmetric vibration), 918cm⁻¹(Al-OH stretching vibration), 780 cm⁻¹(Al-O stretching vibration), 516 cm⁻¹(Si-O-Al bending vibration) and 470 cm⁻¹(Si-O in-plane bending vibration) were observed in Taungnauk kaolinite sample. According to FTIR data, the bands at 1033 cm⁻¹(Si-O symmetric stretching vibration), 918 cm⁻¹(Al-OH stretching vibration), 787 cm⁻¹(Al-O stretching vibration), 517 cm⁻¹(Si-O-Al bending vibration) and 447 cm⁻¹(Si-O in-plane bending vibration) were observed in Tigyit fly ash sample.

Figure 7. XRD diffractograms of kaolinite and fly ash samples

Figure 8. SEM images of kaolinite samples

Figure 9 SEM images of fly ash samples

Figure 10. FTIR spectra of (a) kaolinite and (b) fly ash samples.

Table 2. FTIR Data of Kaolinite (Taungnauk) and Fly Ash (Tigyt) Samples

	Wave Number (cm ⁻¹) Kaolinite		Wave Number (cm ⁻¹) Fly Ash		Band Assignment* (Functional Group)
	Observed	Literature	Observed	Literature	
1	1095	1086	1033	1033	Si-O stretching vibration
2	918	914	918	914	Al-OH stretching vibration
3	780	798	787	794	Al-O stretching vibration
4	516	539	517	537	Si-O-Al bending vibration
5	470	470	447	467	Si-O in-plane bending vibration

* Yunsheng *et al.*, (2006) and Van Jassrsveld *et al.*, (2002)

Thermal Analysis Data (TG-DTA) of Kaolinite Sample

TG-DTA thermograms of kaolinite samples are shown in Figures 11 (a) and 11 (b). The breaks in temperature, corresponding to dehydration, decomposition temperatures of kaolinite samples were observed in these thermograms. Heating temperatures were changed from (38-600) °C. According to TG-DTA curves, the maximum weight loss percent of these samples are observed as presented in Table 3. It can be found that the weight loss was 7.476% for Taungnauk kaolinite sample and 11.474% for Kyauktaga kaolinite sample.

(a) Taungnauk sample

(b) Kyauktaga sample

Figure 11. TG-DTA thermograms of kaolinite samples

Table 3. Thermal Analysis Data (TG-DTA) of Kaolinite Sample

Kaolinite Sample	Temperature Range (°C)	Weight Loss (%)	Remark
Taungnauk	38.26 - 598.82	7.476	Dehydration due to surface and absorbed water
Kyauktaga	38.22 - 465.90	3.175	Dehydration due to surface and absorbed water
	465.90 - 600.93	8.299	Phase change due to decomposition

Mechanical Properties of Prepared Geopolymers

The compressive strength is one of the most noteworthy properties of hardened geopolymer and is considered as the characteristic material value (Nugteren and Izquierdo, 2009). It can be observed that the compressive strength increases almost linearly with kaolinite to fly ash ratio up to 4:3 (Table 4). The highest geopolymer strength was reached 93.41 MPa in pressure after 28 days for geopolymer sample H1 (Djwantoro *et al.*, 2004).

Tensile strength development of geopolymer incorporating various proportions of kaolinite and fly ash are reported in Table 4. Maximum tensile strength of 280 psi for geopolymer sample H1 was obtained for 56 days. From these data, it was observed that geopolymer samples (H1-H4) were achieved the highest tensile strength. The histograms of compressive and tensile strengths of kaolinite and fly ash-based geopolymers are shown in Figures 12 (a) and 12 (b) (Djwantoro *et al.*, 2008).

Out of thirty six prepared geopolymers, the four geopolymer samples (H1-H4) were selected from mechanical properties, such as compressive strength, tensile strength and acid resistant tests. Therefore, these four prepared geopolymer samples (H1-H4) were chosen for application. It can be concluded that prepared Pb, Cd and As loaded kaolinite and fly ash-based geopolymer samples (H1-H4) were chosen for immobilization of toxic metal ions (Pb^{2+} , Cd^{2+} and As^{3+}) and suitable for removal of toxic metal ions from industrial wastewater samples.

Figure 12. Histograms of (a) compressive strength and (b) tensile strength of prepared geopolymer samples

Table 4. Compressive Strength (MPa) and Tensile Strength (psi) for Prepared Geopolymers

Geopolymer sample	Compressive Strength (28 days)	Tensile Strength (28 days)	Tensile Strength (56 days)
G-1	77.84	136	202
G-2	17.86	149	209
G-3	23.22	218	245
G-4	20.49	12	72
H-1	93.41	244	280
H-2	35.36	87	110
H-3	79.85	220	278
H-4	43.07	154	158
I-1	39.38	195	206
I-2	15.31	68	96
I-3	36.72	212	226
I-4	19.04	0	4

Characterization of Prepared Geopolymers

SEM analysis was also used to describe the morphology of kaolinite and fly ash-based prepared geopolymer samples. The scanning electron micrographs of the prepared geopolymer samples (**H1-H4**) were obtained at the age of 28 days. From micrographs as shown in Figure 13, it can be observed that the microstructure of kaolinite and fly ash-based geopolymer samples by increasing silica and alumina contents, the morphology changed and a more integrated phase occurred and thus the strength increased (Frantisek *et al.*, 2006).

Relative quantitative elemental determination for kaolinite and fly ash-based prepared geopolymer samples (**H1-H4**) were semi-quantitatively analyzed by using EDXRF technique. From EDXRF measurement, prepared geopolymers had been found the highest percent of silica content in all these samples. XRD analysis was carried out to identify new formed phases and the degree of amorphicity. X-ray powder diffraction patterns of kaolinite and fly ash-based geopolymer samples (**H1-H4**) are shown in Figure 14. New amorphous aluminosilicate phases, such as natrolite ($\text{Na}_2\text{Al}_2\text{Si}_3\text{O}_{10}$), hydroxysodalite ($\text{Na}_4\text{Al}_3\text{Si}_3\text{O}_{12}\text{OH}$) and sodium aluminium silicate ($\text{Na}_{1.84}\text{Al}_2\text{Si}_{2.88}\text{O}_{9.68}$) contributes improvement in compressive strength as shown in Table 5 (Ravindra and Ghosh 2009).

Thermal stability of kaolinite and fly ash-based prepared geopolymers were investigated by TG-DTA analysis. All of the prepared geopolymer samples were found to be

initial weight loss at about 36°C, likely a result of moisture evaporation upon heating. According to these thermograms, geopolymer sample (H1) was found to be lowest weight loss (8.473%) among these all geopolymer samples.

Figure 13. SEM images of kaolinite and fly ash-based geopolymer samples (H1-H4)

Figure 14. XRD diffractograms of prepared geopolymer samples (H1 –H4)

Table 5. XRD Results for Prepared Geopolymer Samples

Geopolymer Sample	Mineral Compounds (Computer Matching)
H-1	*Natrolite, **Hydroxysodalite
H-2	Natrolite, Hydroxysodalite, Sodium Aluminium Silicate
H-3	Natrolite, Hydroxysodalite, Sodium Aluminium Silicate
H-4	Natrolite, Hydroxysodalite,

* (Ravindra and Ghosh, 2009)

** (Zaharali *et al.*, 2009)

Study on FT IR Spectra

The FT IR spectrum of kaolinite and fly ash-based prepared geopolymer sample H1 (i.e., a source materials as Taungnauk kaolinite and Tigyit fly ash samples) is shown in Figure 15. According to Table 6, it can be observed that Si-O stretching vibrations in original fly ash was 1033.61 cm⁻¹, while it was shifted to lower values in geopolymer (H1) around 1018.45 cm⁻¹. A 918.15cm⁻¹ in IR spectrum of kaolinite caused by six-coordinated Al-OH stretching vibration, become very weak in IR spectrum of kaolinite and fly ash-based geopolymer H1 (Frantisek *et al.*, 2006).

Figure 15. FT IR spectrum of kaolinite and fly ash-based prepared geopolymer sample (H1)

Table 6. IR Bands and their Corresponding Species of Kaolinite, Fly Ash and Prepared Geopolymer Sample (H1)

Types of Species	Wave No. (cm ⁻¹)	Band Assignment
Si-O	1018.45	Si-O symmetric stretching vibration
Al-OH	Very weak	six-coordinated Al-OH stretching vibration
Al-O	786.98	six-coordinated Al-O stretching vibration
Si -O	Very weak	Si-O bending vibration
Si-O-Al	532.37	Si-O-Al bending vibration
Si-O	447.50	Si-O in-plane bending vibration

Characterization of Prepared Metal Loaded Kaolinite and Fly Ash-based Geopolymers

Scanning electron microscope analysis was utilized to examine the micrographic nature of Pb and Cd loaded geopolymer samples (H1-H3). The surface morphology of Pb²⁺ and Cd²⁺ loaded on kaolinite and fly ash-based geopolymers H1 and H3 are shown in Figure 16. It can be clearly seen the visual inspection of external porosity and morphology (Van Jaarsveld and Van Deventer, 1999). The XRD diffractograms of Pb, Cd and As loaded geopolymer samples (H1 and H3) are shown in Figure 17. The presence of peaks related to Pb, Cd and As were clearly seen in the XRD diffractograms. Moreover, metal ions sorbed diffractograms clearly indicated the specific sharp peaks at respective higher 2θ values (Yunsheng *et al.*, 2006).

Pb loaded geopolymer

Cd loaded geopolymer

Figure 16. SEM images of Pb and Cd loaded prepared geopolymer samples (H1 & H3)

Pb loaded geopolymer H 1

Cd loaded geopolymer H1

As loaded geopolymer H 1

Pb loaded geopolymer H 3

Cd loaded geopolymer H 3

As loaded geopolymer H 3

Figure 17. XRD diffractograms of Pb, Cd and As loaded prepared geopolymers

Leaching Behaviors of Prepared Geopolymer Samples

Geopolymer samples (H1- H4) contained identical amounts of Pb, Cd and As and therefore leaching results can be compared on the same basic. These results are presented in Table 7 and shown in Figure 18. For instance, the immobilization efficiency was in the order of 92.90 % for Pb^{2+} , 86.20% for Cd^{2+} and 83.80% for As^{3+} after 24 h leaching tests as shown in Figure 19. However, when the mixture of heavy metal ions were introduced, the immobilization capacity will rapidly reduced, which is clearly seen in Table 8. The immobilization efficiency of mixture of metal ions by kaolinite and fly ash-based metal loaded geopolymer (H1) is presented in Table 9. The immobilization efficiency for the multiple species of metal ions in mixture is in the order of 45.90% for Pb^{2+} , 32.80% for Cd^{2+} and 21.00% for As^{3+} . It was also noted that two of the main factors influencing the incorporation of ions into a geopolymer structure were thought to be ionic size and valence of a specific ion (Zongjin *et al.*, 2009). It was obvious that the immobilization efficiency of multiple species metal ions was slightly lower than that of single species metal ions (Table 9), which may be due to the increased mass transfer resistance that caused by the presence of more metal ions in the solutions (Santoshkumar and Equeenuddin, 2010).

Table 7. Immobilization Efficiency of Pb^{2+} , Cd^{2+} and As^{3+} Ions by Kaolinite and Fly Ash-based Metal Loaded prepared Geopolymer Samples (H1-H4) as a Function of Contact Time

Geo-polymer	Immobilization Efficiency (%)								
	Pb^{2+}			Cd^{2+}			As^{3+}		
	(2h)	(8h)	(24h)	(2h)	(8h)	(24h)	(2h)	(8h)	(24h)
H-1	91.10	92.50	92.90	85.70	85.90	86.20	82.70	83.40	83.80
H-2	88.50	89.10	89.40	83.90	84.50	84.90	81.90	82.30	82.80
H-3	90.30	90.90	91.30	85.20	85.70	85.90	82.30	82.90	83.30
H-4	88.70	89.00	89.20	84.20	84.80	85.10	82.10	82.40	83.00

Table 8. Immobilization Efficiency of Mixture of Pb^{2+} , Cd^{2+} and As^{3+} Ions by kaolinite and Fly Ash-based Metal Loaded Prepared Geopolymer Samples (H1-H4)

Geopolymer	Metal Ions Mixture (multiple species)			Metal Ion Only (single ion species)		
	Pb^{2+}	Cd^{2+}	As^{3+}	Pb^{2+}	Cd^{2+}	As^{3+}
H-1	45.90	32.80	21.00	92.90	86.20	83.80
H-2	43.10	31.60	20.20	89.40	84.90	82.80
H-3	44.70	31.90	20.80	91.30	85.90	83.30
H-4	43.50	31.20	19.80	89.20	85.10	83.00

Table 9 Immobilization Efficiency of Mixture of Pb^{2+} , Cd^{2+} and As^{3+} Ions by Kaolinite and Fly Ash-based Metal Loaded Prepared Geopolymer Sample (H1)

Metal Ions	Immobilization Efficiency (%)	
	Metal Ions Mixture (multiple species)	Metal Ion Only (single ion species)
Pb^{2+}	45.90	92.90
Cd^{2+}	32.80	86.20
As^{3+}	21.00	83.80

Figure 18. Immobilization efficiency of Pb^{2+} , Cd^{2+} and As^{3+} ions by kaolinite and fly ash-based metal loaded prepared geopolymer samples (H1-H4) as a function of contact time (24h)

Figure 19. Relation between Immobilization efficiency of Pb^{2+} , Cd^{2+} and As^{3+} ions by (Pb, Cd and As) loaded prepared geopolymer samples (H1 -H4) (24h)

Removal of Toxic Metal Ions from Wastewater Samples by AAS

The metal ions (Pb^{2+} , Cd^{2+} and As^{3+}) concentrations in industrial wastewater were determined by atomic absorption spectrophotometer (AAS). The concentrations of toxic metal ions in wastewater samples from different industries are presented in Table 10. On the average lead concentration of 0.568 ppm, cadmium concentration of 4.254 ppm and arsenic concentration of 2.009 ppm were found to be contained in industrial wastewater from Textile Mills at Wundwin. As^{3+} ion in wastewater sample from Battery Industry at Shwe Pyi Thar was found to be 1.11 ppm. Therefore, among these industrial wastewater samples, two samples from Textile Mills in Wundwin and Battery Industry in Shwe Pyi Thar were chosen for removal of toxic metal ions by prepared geopolymers (H1-H4) (Tables 11 and 12).

On examination of the resulting data of Wundwin wastewater, the removal percent of prepared geopolymer H1 were 67.5% for lead, 59.5% for cadmium and 52.5% for arsenic, respectively. And also the resulting data of Shwe Pyi Thar wastewater showed the removal efficiencies of prepared geopolymer H1 as 65.7% of lead and 49.4% of arsenic, respectively.

The composition of toxic metal ions in industrial wastewater samples before and after treatment with prepared geopolymer H1 are presented in Tables 13 for (Wundwin) and 14 for (Shwe Pyi Thar) (Figures 20 (a) and 20 (b)).

Table 10. Concentration of Toxic Metal Ions in Wastewater Samples by AAS

Wastewater Sample	pH	Pb ²⁺ (ppm)	Cd ²⁺ (ppm)	As ³⁺ (ppm)	Source
Wundwin	6.92	0.568	4.254	2.009	Textile Mills
Shwe Pyi Thar	4.40	0.692	ND	1.118	Battery Industry
Okkyin	6.65	0.589	ND	ND	Aluminium Wares Factory
Taunggyi	7.27	0.576	ND	ND	Metal smelting Factory

Table 11. Removal (%) of Toxic Metal Ions from Wastewater (Textile Mills) by Kaolinite and Fly Ash- based Prepared Geopolymer Samples (H1-H4)

Geopolymer Sample	Concentration of Metal Ions					
	Pb ²⁺		Cd ²⁺		As ³⁺	
	ppm	Removal (%)	ppm	Removal (%)	ppm	Removal (%)
H 1	0.187	67.1	1.731	59.3	0.955	52.5
H 2	0.271	52.3	2.136	49.8	1.056	47.4
H 3	0.212	62.6	1.889	55.6	0.973	51.6
H 4	0.229	59.7	2.138	49.7	1.052	47.7

Table 12. Removal (%) of Toxic Metal Ions from Wastewater (Battery Industry) by Kaolinite and Fly Ash- based Prepared Geopolymer Samples (H1-H4)

Geopolymer Sample	Concentration of Metal Ions			
	Pb ²⁺ (ppm)	Removal (%)	As ³⁺ (ppm)	Removal (%)
H 1	0.238	65.7	0.565	49.4
H 2	0.335	51.6	0.628	43.9
H 3	0.260	62.4	0.593	46.9
H 4	0.331	52.2	0.621	44.4

Table 13. Compositions of Toxic Metal Ions in Wastewater Sample (WD) Before and After Treatment with Kaolinite and Fly Ash-based Prepared Geopolymer (H1)

Metal Ions	Concentration of Metal Ions (ppm)		
	Before Treatment	After Treatment	Removal (%)
Pb ²⁺	0.568	0.187	67.1
Cd ²⁺	4.254	1.731	59.3
As ³⁺	2.009	0.955	52.5

Table 14. Compositions of Toxic Metal Ions in Wastewater Sample (SPT) Before and After Treatment with Kaolinite and Fly Ash-based Prepared Geopolymer (H1)

Metal Ions	Concentration of Metal Ions (ppm)		
	Before Treatment	After Treatment	Removal (%)
Pb ²⁺	0.692	0.238	65.7
As ³⁺	1.118	0.565	49.4

Figure 20. (a) Removal percent of Pb²⁺, Cd²⁺ and As³⁺ ions in wastewater from Textile Mills (Wundwin) and (b) Battery Industry (Shwe Pyi Thar) by kaolinite and fly ash-based prepared geopolymer samples (H1 - H4)

Conclusion

According to conventional analysis data, SiO₂, Al₂O₃, Fe₂O₃, CaO and MgO were found in both kaolinite and fly ash and samples. From SEM micrographs, kaolinite samples were observed as crystalline nature. From the XRD diffractograms, SiO₂ (silica) and Al₂O₃ (alumina) were observed in both kaolinite and fly ash samples. FTIR data indicated the presence of Si-O and Al-O functional group in both kaolinite and fly ash sample. TG-DTA curves indicated the maximum weight loss percent of (11.474%) in Kyauktaga kaolinite, whereas the minimum weight loss percent of (7.476%) in Taungnauk kaolinite.

The compressive strength of geopolymers H1 and H3 increased 93.41 MPa and 79.85MPa, respectively. The tensile strength of 244 psi and 220 psi were obtained for geopolymers (H1 and H3) cured at room temperature for 28 days. However, the longer curing time improved the geopolymerization processes resulting in higher tensile strength for geopolymer H1 (280 psi) and geopolymer H3 (278psi) after 56 days. According to SEM analysis, the microstructure of kaolinite and fly ash- based prepared geopolymer samples may be viewed as composites comprising of aluminosilicate gel phase and partially reacted fly ash particles. XRD analysis was carried out to identify new formed phases and the degree of amorphicity. The most characteristic difference observed between FTIR spectra of kaolinite, fly ash and geopolymer (H1) were shifted of the band attributed to the symmetric vibrations of Si-O-Si bond.

XRD pattern of metal loaded kaolinite and fly ash-based prepared geopolymer samples showed the presence of Pb, Cd and As in the respective XRD diffractograms. The 2θ peaks in XRD patterns of the metal loaded prepared geopolymer samples were well matched with Pb, Cd and As peaks in standard peaks of geopolymers.

In this work, the immobilization of toxic metal ions such as Pb(II), Cd(II) and As(III) ions onto different kaolinite and fly ash-based geopolymer samples (H1-H4) were studied. The

immobilization efficiency exceeds 92.9% when Pb contained in metal loaded geopolymer. It was worth noting that Pb shows better immobilization efficiency than Cd and As in the case of both metal ion only and metal ions mixture.

Removal percents of Pb^{2+} , Cd^{2+} and As^{3+} ions from wastewater samples (Wundwin) were found to be in the range of 67.1%, 59.3% and 52.5%, respectively, using geopolymer H1. For Shwe Pyi Thar wastewater sample, the removal percents were observed 65.7% for Pb^{2+} and 49.4% for As^{3+} ions. It was found that sorption efficiency was in the order of $Pb^{2+} > Cd^{2+} > As^{3+}$. Among the four geopolymer samples, geopolymer sample (H1) showed the maximum leaching property. This observation was consistent with the results from mechanical properties (i.e., compressive and tensile strength).

The process of removing the metal ions (Pb^{2+} , Cd^{2+} and As^{3+}) from wastewater samples by kaolinite and fly ash-based geopolymer (H1) were found to be used as an effective aluminosilicate polymeric material in the treatment of industrial influents. Thus, this type of geopolymer is one of the materials which normally use for heavy metal immobilization with lower cost and simpler process in the present work.

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